

PENTABASIS AND AGE-RELATED PENTAPSYCHOLOGY

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Abstract

The application of the structural-functional approach to the study of the human psyche is explored. To analyze personality, a five-component approach (pentapsychology) is used, and to analyze the human psyche as a whole, an eight-component approach (octanalysis) is used. The properties of five components (instances) of personality are analyzed: three instances of consciousness and two instances of the unconscious. The question of the personality instances hierarchy is considered. It is shown that human behavior and the effectiveness of his activities largely depend on the instances hierarchy of his personality chosen by a person. The application of the five-component approach to describe the psychological properties of both the personality and to describe the psychological properties of any association of the personalities (family, society, state, country, civilization) is analyzed. The Pentabasis is considered - a five-level worldview model proposed by the administration of the President of Russia as a value ideology of Russian society. Age-related pentapsychology, a section of pentapsychology, explains the essence of Pentabasis and offers a practice-tested methodology for selecting personnel to increase the effectiveness of large-scale application of Pentabasis in the life of the country.

Keywords: five-component theory of personality, octanalysis, personality psychology, Pentabasis, age-related pentapsychology

Introduction

In the field of science, structural-functional analysis is often used to obtain reliable knowledge.

Although the human psyche is invisible, such an analysis is quite applicable for studying the human psyche and studying the properties of his personality.

To describe the properties of the human psyche, the Austrian psychologist, psychoanalyst, psychiatrist and neurologist Sigmund Freud (1856-1939) was the first to use structural-functional analysis. He proposed a three-component structural model of the psyche. Of course, the three-component approach is not sufficient to describe the psyche.

The author's detailed study of personality traits shows that to obtain reliable knowledge about personality traits, it is necessary to use a five-component approach (pentapsychology), and to describe the human psyche as a whole, an eight-component approach (octanalysis) [1-23]. Pentapsychology and octanalysis were created on the basis of the article by Yatsenko V.I. "Five-component theory of personality" [1], registered by the Russian Society of Authors. All rights reserved. © Yatsenko V. I. 2002

Pentapsychology notes that the five-component approach is applicable to describe the psychological properties of both an individual person and to describe the psychological properties of any association of individuals (family, society, state, country, civilization).

Currently, government structures in some countries set as their goal the use of a five-component approach of psychology to solve the problem of "Development and Improvement" in the following areas: personality, family, society, state, country, civilization.

For example, since 2022, Pentabasis [24] has been known - a five-level worldview model proposed by the

administration of the President of Russia as a value ideology of Russian society.

A comparison of Pentabasis and pentapsychology shows that when developing Pentabasis, a five-component approach to personality analysis and a hierarchy of personality instances were used, which are considered in age-related pentapsychology, a section of pentapsychology.

Let's consider the possibilities of using age-related pentapsychology to explain the essence of Pentabasis and the effective use of Pentabasis in the life of the country.

Description of Pentabasis

The Pentabasis methodological model consists of five blocks: person, family, society, state, country. They are described in detail in the scientific article "Perception of basic values, factors and structures socio-historical development of Russia" (Journal of Political Research, Vol. 6 No. 3, 2022). Its authors include the head of the department for ensuring the activities of the State Council Alexander Dmitrievich Kharichev, the ideologist of the "DNA of Russia" Andrei Vladimirovich Polossin, the dean of the Faculty of Political Science of Moscow State University Andrei Yurievich Shutov and the head of the department of strategic research and forecasting of the Expert Institute of Social Research (EISR) Ekaterina Nikitichna Sokolova.

Pentabasis is a set of key value principles, including basic attitudes, norms and ideals that determine the behavior and interaction of members of society. These principles form the basis of the sociocultural system and determine its structure.

A system of five components, each of which has its own value dominant:

Person - Creation

Family - Traditions
 Society - Consent
 State – Trust in institutions
 Country - Patriotism.

The Pentabasis components may differ and have variations depending on the specific time, historical and cultural context, but they are universal and human universal, as they reflect the basic needs and aspirations of society. [24].

Description of age-related pentapsychology

Pentapsychology studies the properties of five components (instances) of personality, which, when performing their functions, dominate the personality in turn. And here the question arises about the supported hierarchy of personality instances.

A person has freedom of choice and can establish in his personality any hierarchy of personality instances. A person's behavior and the effectiveness of his activities largely depend on the supported hierarchy of personality instances.

In pentapsychology, five instances of personality are designated: three instances of consciousness 5-Soul, 4-Heart, 1-Mind and two instances of the unconscious 3-Irratio, 2-Ratio. In this designation, the numbers 5, 4, 3, 2, 1 show the place of personality instance in natural, harmonious hierarchy of personality instances, from top to bottom, 54321-hierarchy.

Pentapsychology discovered a fundamental property of personality: a harmonious hierarchy of instances of individual consciousness - 541-hierarchy: 5-Soul - in first place, 4-Heart - in second, 1-Mind - in third place.

In 2010, using pentapsychology methods, the effect of innate dominance of personality instances was discovered [4].

Depending on the date of birth of a person, the five instances of his personality differ significantly from each other in the degree of innate dominance. The octanalytic personality formula and the octanalytic personality code show the degree of innate dominance of each of five personality instances.

The innate dominance of personality instances significantly influences a person's behavior and the effectiveness of his activities. The degree of innate dominance of personality instance persists throughout a person's life and makes it possible to predict the characteristics of a person's behavior in various life situations [13-18].

Age-related pentapsychology notes that five personality instances begin to show age-related activity at different periods of a person's life in the sequence: 3-Irratio, 2-Ratio, 1-Mind, 4-Heart, 5-Soul.

In the prenatal period, from conception to the birth of a child, only one instance of the unconscious 3-Irratio shows age-related activity in the child's personality.

During the period of innocent childhood, from birth to 1.5 – 2 years, two instances of the unconscious, 3-Irratio and 2-Ratio, show age-related activity in the baby's personality.

In the preschool period, from 1.5 – 2 years to 6 years, three instances of Stephen Karpman's dramatic triangle show age-related activity in the child's personality: two instances of the unconscious 3-Irratio (role

Victim), 2-Ratio (role Rescuer) and one instance of consciousness 1-Mind (role Pursuer).

During the school period, from 6 years to 18 years, in personality of a child or teenager, already four instances show age-related activity: two instances of the unconscious 3-Irratio, 2-Ratio and two instances of consciousness 4-Heart, 1-Mind. During this period, a crisis of adolescence may manifest itself: the dual power of the instances of consciousness 4-Heart (friendliness) and 1-Mind (selfishness). As soon as the choice of consciousness instances hierarchy is made (41-hierarchy or 14-hierarchy), the crisis ends.

During the period of adult life, from the age of 18, all five personality instances show age-related activity in personality of an adult: two instances of the unconscious 3-Irratio, 2-Ratio and three instances of consciousness 5-Soul, 4-Heart, 1-Mind. During this period, a midlife crisis may manifest itself: the dual power of consciousness instances 4-Heart (friendliness) and 5-Soul (altruism). As soon as the choice of consciousness instances hierarchy is made (45-hierarchy or 54-hierarchy), the crisis ends.

Properties of emotionally unstable instances of the unconscious:

- instance-extrovert 3-Irratio – creativity, irrationality, spontaneity of actions, in Eric Berne's transactional analysis the state Child, according to Stephen Karpman the role of Victim, the temperament type choleric;

- instance-introvert 2-Ratio – rational, logical actions, following traditions, laws, agreements, practicality of actions, in Eric Berne's transactional analysis the state Parent, according to Stephen Karpman the role Rescuer, the temperament type melancholic.

Properties of emotionally stable instances of consciousness:

- instance-extrovert 1-Mind – intellectual abilities, building relationships according to the scheme “I am higher, you are lower”, egoism, a sense of superiority, unprincipledness, deceit, aggressiveness, betrayal, according to Stephen Karpman the role Persecutor, the desire for entertainment, getting personal pleasure, enjoyment, conspicuous consumption, the tendency to give preference to short-term happiness over long-term satisfaction and personal growth, the temperament type sanguine, the implementation of independent conscious intellectual choice;

- instance-introvert 4-Heart – managerial abilities, building relationships according to the scheme “I and you are on the same level”, friendliness, equality, brotherhood, heartfelt relationships, in Eric Berne's transactional analysis the state Adult, the temperament type phlegmatic, the implementation of independent conscious management choice;

- instance-extrovert 5-Soul – building relationships according to the scheme “You are higher, I am lower”, altruism, submission, service, devotion, sacrifice, the temperament type sanguine, the implementation of independent conscious emotional choice.

Age-related pentapsychology notes that three instances of consciousness (5-Soul, 4-Heart, 1-Mind) begin to show age-related activity in the sequence: 1-Mind (from 1.5 - 2 years of age), 4-Heart (from 6 years

of age), 5-Soul (from 18 years of age). Such a sequence is directly opposite to the irreproachable 541-hierarchy of consciousness instances and is the reason for the emergence in a person of a false idea of reality.

In the absence of purposeful, systematic formation of the personality of a child or teenager, he may have the erroneous idea that the 145-hierarchy is a natural hierarchy of consciousness instances and this hierarchy must be observed.

Depending on the innate dominant properties of the individual, living conditions and upbringing, a teenager can be formed a 14-hierarchy or 41-hierarchy of consciousness instances, and an adult can be formed a 145-, 154-, 415-, 451-, 514- or 541-hierarchy of consciousness instances.

When forming a harmoniously developed personality in a child, teenager, or adult, the task of pedagogy is, first of all, the formation in their consciousness of a harmonious 541-hierarchy of instances.

Five value dominants of Pentabasis and five instances of personality

Let's compare the five value dominants of Pentabasis and the five instances of personality in pentapsychology:

- "PERSON (creation)" – instance 3-Irratio, creativity, irrational actions;
- "FAMILY (traditions)" – instance 2-Ratio, rational actions;
- "SOCIETY (consent)" – instance 1-Mind, analytical abilities, use of mind to achieve agreement;
- "STATE (trust in institutions)" – instance 4-Heart, managerial abilities, managerial actions based on friendliness, counteraction to the "fifth column";
- "COUNTRY (patriotism)" – instance 5-Soul, service, devotion, sacrifice, altruism for the sake of preserving the sovereignty of the country.

Selection of personnel for the use of Pentabasis

The comparison of Pentabasis and pentapsychology shows which instance of personality, when selecting personnel, should show innate dominance in order to increase the effectiveness of the implementation of the value dominants of Pentabasis:

- instance 5-Soul – "COUNTRY (patriotism)";
- instance 4-Heart – "STATE (trust in institutions)";
- instance 3-Irratio – "PERSON (creation)";
- instance 2-Ratio – "FAMILY (traditions)";
- instance 1-Mind – "SOCIETY (consent)".

Based on the octanalytic personality code, it is possible to select a candidate whose necessary instance of personality shows a high degree of innate dominance.

For example, to implement the value dominant of Pentabasis "COUNTRY (patriotism)", first of all, people with the innate dominance of the instance 5-Soul are needed. Pentapsychology notes that people born in a year ending in digit 2 or digit 3, for example, 2012, 2013, 2022, 2023, have such innate dominant personality traits.

Conclusions and offers

Age-related pentapsychology clearly explains the essence of Pentabasis. Pentapsychology also offers a practice-tested recruitment methodology to increase the effectiveness of the large-scale application of Pentabasis in the life of the country.

Compiling an octanalytic personality formula

Compiling an octanalytic personality formula makes it possible to reveal the congenital dominance of the personality instances. In the state of personality instance dominance, in the psyche, the properties of this personality instance are manifested first of all. The professional choice of a person, his behavior, character traits to a large extent depend on such a congenital tendency of personality instances to dominate.

Octanalysis studies the five instances of personality 5-Soul, 4-Heart, 3-Irratio, 2-Ratio, 1-Mind. Before the name of an instance, its serial number in the natural hierarchy of instances is indicated, from top to bottom: 5, 4, 3, 2, 1.

The study of personality with the help of octanalysis shows that in each person, depending on the date of birth, from two to five instances of personality have a congenital inclination to dominance.

In octanalysis, a method has been developed for compiling an octanalytic personality formula, which reveals the "First Dominant" and "Second Dominant" - congenitally dominant instances of personality associated with the date of birth of a person. The dominance of first dominant is more pronounced than the dominance of second dominant.

This congenital dominance of the personality instance manifests itself to the same extent throughout a person's life, regardless of the conditions of his life.

The term "octanalytic personality formula" used in octanalysis is substantiated by numerous tests in practice of the characteristics of such a formula when describing the properties of the psyche of specific people.

Dear reader! Below is a table with which you can independently create an octanalytic personality formula for any person by the date of his birth.

To describe the properties of the human psyche on the basis of the octanalytic personality formula, it is necessary to use not only the Table, but also to know in detail the properties of personality instances 5-Soul, 4-Heart, 3-Irratio, 2-Ratio, 1-Mind. Numerous properties of these instances are described in articles on octanalysis on the website "Eight instances of the psyche" www.8-in.com.

Key properties of five instances of personality:

- instance of consciousness 5-Soul - service, sacrifice, altruism;
- instance of consciousness 4-Heart - managerial abilities;
- instance of the unconscious 3-Irratio - creative abilities;
- instance of the unconscious 2-Ratio - rational abilities;
- instance of consciousness 1-Mind - analytical abilities, selfishness.

Table.

Compiling an octanalytic personality formula by date of birth

43-Ox	32-Tiger	23-Rabbit	13-Dragon	42-Snake	31-Horse
19.02.1901	08.02.1902	29.01.1903	16.02.1904	04.02.1905	25.01.1906
06.02.1913	26.01.1914	14.02.1915	03.02.1916	23.01.1917	11.02.1918
24.01.1925	13.02.1926	02.02.1927	23.01.1928	10.02.1929	30.01.1930
11.02.1937	31.01.1938	19.02.1939	08.02.1940	27.01.1941	15.02.1942
29.01.1949	17.02.1950	06.02.1951	27.01.1952	14.02.1953	03.02.1954
15.02.1961	05.02.1962	25.01.1963	13.02.1964	02.02.1965	21.01.1966
03.02.1973	23.01.1974	11.02.1975	31.01.1976	18.02.1977	07.02.1978
20.02.1985	09.02.1986	29.01.1987	17.02.1988	06.02.1989	27.01.1990
07.02.1997	27.01.1998	16.02.1999	05.02.2000	24.01.2001	12.02.2002
26.01.2009	10.02.2010	03.02.2011	23.01.2012	10.02.2013	31.01.2014
12.02.2021	01.02.2022	22.01.2023	10.02.2024	29.01.2025	17.02.2026
21-Goat	12-Monkey	41-Rooster	34-Dog	24-Pig	14-Rat
13.02.1907	02.02.1908	22.01.1909	10.02.1910	30.01.1911	18.02.1912
01.02.1919	20.02.1920	08.02.1921	28.01.1922	16.02.1923	05.02.1924
17.02.1931	06.02.1932	26.01.1933	14.02.1934	04.02.1935	24.01.1936
05.02.1943	25.01.1944	13.02.1945	02.02.1946	22.01.1947	10.02.1948
24.01.1955	12.02.1956	31.01.1957	18.02.1958	08.02.1959	28.01.1960
09.02.1967	30.01.1968	17.02.1969	06.02.1970	27.01.1971	15.02.1972
28.01.1979	16.02.1980	05.02.1981	25.01.1982	13.02.1983	02.02.1984
15.02.1991	04.02.1992	23.01.1993	10.02.1994	31.01.1995	19.02.1996
01.02.2003	22.01.2004	09.02.2005	29.01.2006	18.02.2007	07.02.2008
19.02.2015	09.02.2016	28.01.2017	16.02.2018	05.02.2019	25.01.2020
06.02.2027	26.01.2028	13.02.2029	03.02.2030	23.01.2031	11.02.2032
Numbers of the dominants - zodiac sign			Period of zodiac sign		
43-Pisces			February 19 - March 20		
32-Aries			March 21 - April 19		
23-Taurus			April 20 - May 20		
13-Gemini			May 21 - June 21		
42-Cancer			June 22 - July 22		
31-Leo			July 23 - August 22		
21- Virgo			August 23 - September 22		
12- Libra			September 23 - October 23		
41- Scorpio			October 24 - November 22		
34- Sagittarius			November 23 - December 21		
24- Capricorn			December 22 - January 20		
14- Aquarius			January 21 - February 18		

In the Table, for each year of birth, the New Year is indicated according to the Eastern calendar. It falls on the second new moon after the winter solstice (after December 21st). In the Gregorian calendar, this usually corresponds to one of the days between January 20 and February 20.

The boundaries of the periods of zodiac signs indicated in the Table are not clearly established and depend on the year of birth. For example, in leap years the boundary shifts slightly. On the boundaries of the periods of zodiac signs, the dates are indicated, transitional from one zodiac sign to another zodiac sign.

The first dominant in the zodiac sign is highlighted in bold. It shows that when the zodiac signs change, the first dominant changes according to the 43214-cycle.

Now let's move on to compiling an octanalytic personality formula.

For example, we need to compile the octanalytic personality formula for the person born on July 2, 1954.

The table shows the start date of 1954 according to the Eastern calendar 02/03/1954. This means that, with a date of birth between 02/03/1954 and 01/23/1955, the entry "31-Horse" should be used. And

with a date of birth from January 01 to February 02, 1954, you must use the entry "42-Snake".

The beginning of the year according to the Eastern calendar falls on the second new moon after the winter solstice and therefore moves between January 20 and February 20.

According to the Table, we find the combination: the zodiac sign of the western calendar 42-Cancer and the sign of the Animal, eastern calendar, 31-Horse. Here "42" means that the First congenital dominant is the instance 4-Heart, and the Second congenital dominant is the instance 2-Ratio. The designation "31" shows that the First Dominant is the instance 3-Irratio, the Second Dominant is the instance 1-Mind.

The designation 42-Cancer shows that with short-term planning of actions for a period of one month or less (short term), the properties of instances 4-Heart (First dominant) and 2-Ratio (Second dominant) are manifested in human behavior, first of all.

The designation 31-Horse shows that with long-term planning of actions for a period of one year or more (long-term perspective), the properties of instances 3-Irratio (First dominant) and 1-Mind (Second

dominant) are manifested in human behavior, first of all.

To describe the state of the psyche "42-Cancer" it is necessary to know in detail the properties of the personality instances 4-Heart and 2-Ratio. And to describe the state of the psyche "31-Horse" it is necessary to thoroughly study the properties of the personality instances 3-Irratio and 1-Mind.

In the given example of compiling an octanalytic personality formula, four instances of personality 4-Heart, 3-Irratio, 2-Ratio and 1-Mind show congenital dominance. But very often there are cases, according to the law of probability of uniform birth of people during the year, when only three or even two instances of personality show congenital dominance, for example, the combination: octanalytic personality formula 34-Sagittarius / 34-Dog, for people born in the period from November 23 to December 21 in 1934, 1946, 1958, 1970, 1982, 1994, 2006. In such cases, a person needs special pedagogical and psychological support during childhood.

The absence of congenital dominance of the personality instance can be partially compensated by the purposeful formation of the acquired dominance of the personality instance through education and training. Such a preventive measure is of great benefit to a person in the implementation of his social and personal adaptation in society. The octanalytic patronage service systematically carries out such preventive measures, and a person's life becomes more comfortable and happy. To register a person with an octanalytic patronage service, it is necessary to diagnose the congenital dominants of his personality. An octanalytic personality formula can be drawn up five minutes after the birth of a child, and this octanalytic formula of a person's personality will be valid throughout his life.

It should be noted that the acquired dominance of the personality instance always manifests itself much weaker than congenital dominance. When performing any work, a person with acquired dominance of personality instance cannot successfully compete with a person who has a congenital dominance of this personality instance.

For example, with the combination 34-Sagittarius / 34-Dog, a person does not have a congenital need for the dominance of instances 1-Mind and 2-Ratio. Such a person does not have a congenital tendency to constantly and deeply analyze the situation and formulate conclusions (properties of consciousness instance 1-Mind). In addition, a person does not have an inclination to constantly comply with any laws, agreements, rules, there is no inclination to perform rational actions, consistent, systematic learning (instance properties of the unconscious 2-Ratio). For such a person, the need for analysis of the situation and rational behavior must be formed through his upbringing and training. And for this, you first need to find out if a person has such a problem. For this purpose, you need to compile an octanalytic personality formula.

Extended octanalytic personality formula

The extended octanalytic personality formula is more accurate. When compiling it, it is necessary to take into account the properties of the so-called background dominant - one of the five instances of personality. The background dominant is determined by the year of a person's birth and manifests itself in a person's behavior as a congenital dominant. Personality instances (5-Soul, 4-Heart, 3-Irratio, 2-Ratio, 1-Mind), as background congenital dominants, uniquely correspond to the elements of "U-sin" (Water, Wood / Air, Fire, Earth, Metal) of Eastern philosophy and the elements (Ether, Water, Fire, Earth, Air) of ancient Greek philosophy.

Based on the data on the properties of elements "U-sin" of Eastern philosophy, every ten years all five instances of personality (5-Soul, 4-Heart, 3-Irratio, 2-Ratio, 1-Mind) dominate as a background dominant, in turn two years in a row.

Instance 1-Mind dominates as background dominant in years ending in 0 and 1. Instance 5-Soul dominates in years ending in 2 and 3. Instance 4-Heart dominates in years ending in 4 and 5. Instance 3-Irratio dominates in years ending in 6 and 7. Instance 2-Ratio dominates in years ending in 8 and 9.

For example, the instance 5-Soul dominates, as a background dominant, in the psyche of people who were born in 2022 and 2023, the instance 4-Heart - for those born in 2024 and 2025, etc. The sequence of changes in years of background dominance of personality instances corresponds to 543215-cycle "Way of the Heart".

The instance of personality, which dominates in the year of birth of a person as a background dominant, is an important congenital factor of the psyche, which it is advisable to take into account when compiling the octanalytic personality formula. In this case, the personality formula will have a different form.

For example, for a date of birth 07/2/1954, the usual personality formula is 42-Cancer / 31-Horse. The last digit of 1954 shows that for this year the background dominant is the personality instance 4-Heart. With this in mind, we write the extended personality formula as follows: 42-Cancer / 4-31-Horse. The entry "4-31-Horse" shows that instance 4-Heart is the congenital background dominant "4" for people born in 1954-1955, and in the combination of dominants "31" the instance 3-Irratio is the first dominant, and the instance 1-Mind is the second dominant. Thus, an additional entry in the personality formula shows that in connection with the background dominance of the instance 4-Heart, his congenital managerial abilities are more clearly manifested.

Refined octanalytic personality formula

The extended octanalytic personality formula discussed above changes in a 60-year cycle, which creates convenience in compiling the formula for people who lived several centuries ago.

In this formula, we took into account the influence of the congenital dominants of the solar zodiac sign, which shows the impact on the human psyche of the state of the Sun against the background of the constel-

lations on the day of his birth. This formula can be refined, taking into account also the influence of innate personality dominants, depending on the lunar zodiac sign, which shows the influence on the human psyche of the state of the Moon against the background of the constellations on the day of his birth.

The lunar zodiac sign has a 19-year cycle of signs (with an accuracy of + 2 hours 5 minutes). The phases of the moon go a day ahead relative to the calculated ones for 219 years.

Let us introduce the notation:

(0%) – the percentage of illumination of the moon in the new moon phase is 0%;

(28% +) – the percentage of illumination of the moon in the waxing moon phase is 28%;

(50% +) – the percentage of illumination of the moon in the "First Quarter" phase is 50%;

(100%) – the percentage of illumination of the moon in the "full moon" phase is 100%;

(50% -) – the percentage of illumination of the moon in the "Third Quarter" phase is 50%;

(23% -) – the percentage of illumination of the moon in the "waning moon" phase is 23%.

For the date of birth 07/2/1954 in the Internet search engine, for the query "moon phase July 2, 1954" we get:

"The current moon phase for July 2nd, 1954 is the Waxing Crescent phase. On this day, the moon is 2.06 days old and 4.59% illuminated with a tilt of -137.099°. The approximate distance from Earth to the moon is 380,083.28 km and the moon sign is Leo".

Then the refined octanalytic personality formula for the date of birth on July 2, 1954 will look like:

3 lunar day / 31-Leo / 4% + // 42-Cancer / 4-31-Horse.

In this formula, the data obtained from the lunar calendar,

"3 lunar day / 31-Leo / 4% +"

provide additional information about the congenital properties of the human psyche.

Octanalytic personality code

Based on the data of the octanalytic personality formula (Formula 1), we compile an octanalytic personality code (Formula 2), which shows the total degree of innate dominance of each of five instances of personality 5-Soul, 4-Heart, 3-Irratio, 2-Ratio, 1-Mind.

Let us assume that the degree of dominance of the First dominant is two points, that of the Second dominant is one point, and that of the background dominant is one point. Then in the octanalytic personality code (Formula 2) the total points is ten.

Octanalytic personality code (Formula 2) has the form

5-Soul/0 points – 4-Heart/3 points – 3-Irratio/4 points – 2-Ratio/1 point – 1-Mind/2 points

or, in shortened form, 5/0 – 4/3 – 3/4 – 2/1 – 1/2, in a more abbreviated form, 034-12.

In the octanalytic personality code (Formula 2), the designation "4-1" shows the total degree of innate dominance for instances of the unconscious: 3-Irratio – 4 points, 2-Ratio – 1 point.

Other digits of the octanalytic personality code show the total degree of innate dominance for the consciousness instances: 5-Soul - 0 points, 4-Heart - 3 points, 1-Mind - 2 points.

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